

Polarographic Determination of Lead(II) and Copper(II) using Phthalhydrazidylazo-2-naphthalenol-6-sulphonic Acid

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Phthalhydrazidylazo-2-naphthalenol-6-sulphonic acid has been found to be a sensitive reagent for polarographic determination of lead(II) and copper(II). Other common metal ions, though do not interfere, cause precipitation when present in large quantities. Very high tolerance of Zn^{2+} and alkaline earth metal ions has been observed in the determination of copper(II).

DURING our investigations¹ on azo derivatives of 3-aminophthalhydrazide†, a water soluble azo compound, phthalhydrazidylazo-2-naphthalenol-6-sulphonic acid, was also synthesised. Examination

of the polarographic behaviour of the compound led to the following methods for determining trace quantities of lead(II) and copper(II). These methods are simpler and more sensitive than similar methods reported earlier for determining these metals^{2,3}.

Experimental

The azo compound was prepared as follows. To a stirred suspension of 3-aminophthalhydrazide⁴ (8.80 g; 0.05 mole) in 6 M hydrochloric acid (30 ml), kept cold below 5° in an ice-salt bath, was added dropwise an aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (3.5 g in 10 ml). The cold mixture was stirred for 1 hr and then filtered quickly to remove any unreacted 3-aminophthalhydrazide. The filtrate, after destroying excess nitrous acid with urea, was added slowly to a stirred and cold solution of 2-naphthalenol-6-sulphonic acid⁵ (11.2 g; 0.05 mole in 100 ml of 50% v/v aqueous ethanol) containing also sodium hydroxide (~ 2 g). The precipitated deep red dye was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised twice from hot water. The dye was further purified by recrystallisation from 50% (v/v) hot aqueous ethanol, when chromatographically pure material (tlc, silica gel), melting at 298-310° was obtained.

For polarography, solutions of AnalaR grade chemicals and chromatographically pure dye were

† Luminol, well known for its chemiluminescence.

prepared in double distilled water. Oxygen-free nitrogen was used to remove dissolved oxygen. Polarograms were obtained at $28 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using an Elico DC recording polarograph (capillary characteristic : $2.068 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$) using saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. Britton-Robinson buffer in the pH range 2-10 was used for recording polarograms of the dye at different pH. An Elico digital pH meter was used to check pH.

Polarograms of the dye at different pH values were obtained from 20 ml of the dye stock solution ($10^{-3} M$) diluted to 100 ml, after adding the required volume of the buffer mixture.

Calibration curve for determining lead :

To a series of 100 ml volumetric flasks each containing the buffer solution was added 20 ml of the dye stock solution followed by different volumes of lead(II) nitrate solution ($10^{-3} M$) so that the quantity of lead(II) in each flask was in the range 0-7 mg. In each case the resulting solution was made upto 100 ml after adding the required quantity of aqueous sodium hydroxide to bring the pH of the solution between 2 and 3. Polarograms between 0 and -1 volt were recorded 30 min after preparing the solutions. Calibration curve was obtained by plotting wave heights against lead concentrations.

Calibration curve for determining copper :

Calibration curve was obtained as in the case of lead, but pH was kept between 6 and 6.5 and quantity of copper in the aqueous solution of copper(II) sulphate used ranged between 0 and 1 mg.

Interference of different metal ions was examined by recording polarograms after incorporating different amounts of these metal ions (as sulphates or as chlorides when sulphates are insoluble) in solutions containing fixed amount of lead(II) or copper(II).

Results and Discussion

The dye gives a single reduction wave in the pH range 2-10. The half-wave potential is dependent

on pH and bears a linear relationship (Fig. 1). The wave is diffusion controlled as evidenced by linear plots of i_d versus \sqrt{h} and i_d versus concentration⁶. The $E_{1/2}$ of the wave showed shift towards negative potentials with increase in pH while the diffusion current remained constant in the entire pH range. Plot of $\log \left[\frac{i}{i_d - i} \right]$ against E_{de} is a straight line indicative of the reversible nature of the process⁶. From the log plot the number of electrons involved in the reduction was calculated as two⁶.

Fig. 1. Dependence of $E_{1/2}$ on pH.

The possible reduction sites in the compound are cyclic $-C=C-$, $-C=N-$ and exocyclic $-C=O$ and $-N=N-$. Of these, the $-N=N-$ group is the most susceptible to reduction⁶. In protolytic solvents such as water, aromatic azo compounds are reported to undergo generally a two electron reduction at the dropping mercury electrode resulting in the hydrazo state⁷⁻⁹.

This reduction path seems plausible also for the azo dye now investigated, since the observed pH dependence of $E_{1/2}$ suggests that proton transfer occurs prior to the first electron intake⁶.

Several water soluble azo dyes, particularly *o,o'*-dihydroxyazo dyes, have been recommended by several investigators for polarographic determination of various metal ions¹⁰, copper being a conspicuous exception. Only one such dye has been found suitable for determining lead. Hence it was of interest to examine the possibility of determining copper(II) and lead(II) using the dye.

Determination of lead(II) :

Minimum interference by different metal ions in the determination of lead using the reagent was found to be at pH 2-3. At this pH, addition of Pb^{2+} causes decrease in the height of the reduction wave of the dye ($E_{1/2} = -0.085$ V) and appearance of an additional wave at more negative potential ($E_{1/2} = -0.395$ V). Such behaviour has been reported in the case of several *o,o'*-dihydroxyazo dyes and the additional wave at more negative potential was attributed to reduction of the metal-complexed dye^{10,11}. Polarograms of the dye recorded in presence of various known concentrations of lead ions showed that decrease of the first and increase of the second wave heights are both directly proportional to the quantity of lead ions present. The second wave was used for preparing the calibration curve (Fig. 2). The relatively low solubility of the dye precludes determination of lead greater than 3×10^{-4} M.

Fig. 2. Calibration curve for lead.

Determination of copper(II) :

At pH 6-6.5, at which interference by other metal ions is the least, the height of the reduction wave of the dye ($E_{1/2} = -0.37$ V) was found to decrease in presence of Cu^{2+} , and no other reduction wave was observed between 0 and -1 volt. The decrease in wave height of the reagent was proportional to the concentration of added copper(II) ions. Calibration curve prepared is given in Fig. 3. A solution of synthesised copper(II) complex of the dye was found non-reducible at this pH. Formation of non-reducible metal complexes has been reported in the case of some *o,o'*-dihydroxyazo dyes and in such cases metal ions were estimated through the decrease in wave height of the reagent¹⁰⁻¹³. Under the condition of estimation, concentration of copper(II) greater than 2×10^{-4} M causes precipitation of the metal complex.

Innumerable determinations of lead(II) and copper(II) based on the calibration curves were

Fig. 3. Calibration curve for copper.

made. The result showed high precision and accuracy. Table 1 brings out a comparative account of the results.

TABLE 1--COMPARISON OF RESULTS OF POLAROGRAPHIC DETERMINATION OF LEAD(II) AND COPPER(II) WITH THOSE OBTAINED BY STANDARD METHODS

Polarographic (mg)	Lead(II)		Polarographic (mg)	Copper(II)	
	Colorimetric** (mg)	Theoretical (mg)		AAS method† (mg)	Theoretical (mg)
0.49	0.49	0.50	0.149	0.148	0.150
0.99	0.99	1.00	0.248	0.247	0.250
1.98	1.98	2.00	0.349	0.348	0.350
2.98	2.97	3.00	0.449	0.448	0.450
3.98	3.98	4.00	0.548	0.547	0.550
4.97	4.96	5.00	0.648	0.647	0.650
5.97	5.96	6.00	0.747	0.748	0.750
6.97	6.97	7.00	0.846	0.847	0.850

† Perkin Elmer 257 atomic absorption spectrometer was used.

Larger amounts of anions such as chloride, sulphate, nitrate and acetate had no effect on the determination of lead(II) or copper(II). The tolerance limit of interfering metal ions is shown in Table 2.

Under the experimental conditions employed for the determination of copper(II) and lead(II), these diverse ions have no influence on the reduction wave(s) within the concentration limits specified in the table. The non-interference of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺ and Zn²⁺ at concentrations exceeding 50 times that of copper is noteworthy.

TABLE 2--NON-INTERFERENCE LIMIT OF METAL IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF LEAD(II) AND COPPER(II)

Metal ion added	Tolerance limits in the determination of	
	Lead(II)	Copper(II)
	1 × 10 ⁻⁵ M	1 × 10 ⁻⁴ M
Fe ²⁺	2.0	1.0
Cr ³⁺	5.0	3.0
Co ²⁺	5.0	1.5
Ni ²⁺	5.0	2.0
Mn ²⁺	15.0	4.0
VO ²⁺	15.0	2.0
Zn ²⁺	25.0	55.0
Mg ²⁺	20.0	100.0
Ca ²⁺	25.0	100.0
Sr ²⁺	30.0	150.0
Ba ²⁺	30.0	60.0

Lead(II) and copper(II) are at fixed concentration of 2 × 10⁻⁴ M and 1.5 × 10⁻⁴ M, respectively.

References

1. N. THANKARAJAN and K. KRISHNAN KUTTY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1977, 46, 487.
2. M. KOPANICA, J. DOLEZAL and J. ZYKA in "Chelates in Analytical Chemistry", (EDS.) H. A. FLASCHKA and A. T. BARNARD, JR., Marcel Dekker, New York, 1967, Vol. 1, p. 205.
3. M. PERKINS and G. F. REYNOLDS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 18, 616, 628.
4. E. H. HUNTRESS, L. N. STANLEY and A. S. PARKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 56, 241.
5. K. H. ENGL and A. W. HATCHISON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 211.
6. P. ZUMAN, "The Elucidation of Organic Electrode Process", Academic Press, New York, 1969.
7. F. G. THOMAS and K. G. BOTO in "Chemistry of Hydrazo, Azo and Azoxy Compounds", (ED.) S. PATAI, Interscience, London, 1975, p. 462.
8. P. T. HILLSON and P. B. BIRNBAUN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, 48, 478.
9. G. PRZATINI, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1973, 69, 796.
10. G. W. LATIMER, JR., *Talanta*, 1968, 15, 1.
11. H. H. WILLARD and J. A. DRAN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, 22, 1264.
12. B. M. SKOBETS and L. N. IVASHENKO, *Ukr. Khim. Zhur.*, 1963, 29, 751; 1964, 30, 279; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 59, 14569; 1964, 60, 13869.
13. J. O. CABRAL and H. A. TARNER, *J. Soc. Dyers Colourists*, 1956, 72, 158.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS and Longman, London, 1978, p. 744.